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ABST 7

A METAGENOMIC STUDY OF BANANA NEMATODE ANTAGONISTS IN CANARY ISLANDS [ESTUDIO METAGENÓMICO SOBRE ANTAGONISTAS DE NEMATODOS DEL BANANO EN LAS ISLAS CANARIAS]

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A study was carried out on the ecology of microbial antagonists associated with phytoparasitic nematodes of banana crops in Canary Islands, Spain. Samples included rhizosphere soil from cv Pequeña enana and controls collected from adjacent sites, without banana. Total RNA was extracted from soil and retrotranscribed. To characterize bacterial communities, the variable V3 and V4 regions of the 16S rRNA ribosomal gene were amplified. The ITS region was used for classification of fungal communities. Libraries were sequenced with an Illumina MiSeq™ in paired ends with 300-bp read length, and analyzed with QIIME and STAMP. Nematodes were extracted from soil by the sieving and decanting technique, counted, and identified with light microscopy. Phytoparasitic nematodes were found mostly in the banana rhizosphere. *Pratylenchus goodeyi* was present in 75% of samples from northern farms at densities of 200-1,750 specimens/100 cm³ soil, with lower prevalence (22%) and densities in the southern fields. *Helicotylenchus* spp. included *H. multicinctus* found in northern and southern farms. Metagenomic data showed several fungal OTUs belonging to Sordariomycetes, including Clavicipitaceae such as *Pochonia chlamydosporia* and *Metarhizium anisopliae*. Other taxa were *Trichoderma harzianum*, *T. longibrachiatum*, *T. virans*, *Beauveria* sp., and *Fusarium* spp., together with mycoparasites such as *Acrostalagmus luteoalbus*. Dominant bacterial phyla were Proteobacteria, Actinobacteria, Planctomycetes, Bacteroidetes, Chloroflexi, and Acidobacteria. Principal coordinate analysis of microbial communities showed a direct effect of cropping on

the samples profiles. Beta-diversity also indicated latitude-related factors that clearly separated northern and southern controls from banana rhizosphere samples.